

WIDE-FIELD INFRARED EXPLORER SPACECRAFT SYSTEM DESIGN

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Abstract- Following a formal and competitive process, the Wide-Field Infrared Explorer (WIRE) instrument was selected in 1994 to become a participant in NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center's Small Explorer Program (SMEX). The WIRE instrument will be used to conduct a deep infrared, extra galactic science survey 500 times more sensitive than the Infrared Astronomy Satellite (IRAS) Faint Source Catalog. The WIRE instrument includes a cryogenically cooled (<7.5K), 128 x 128 pixel, long wave, infrared detector embedded within an optical assembly which is cooled by a two-stage, solid-hydrogen cryostat. The WIRE spacecraft is being configured to be placed into a 470 x 540 km sun-synchronous orbit using an Orbital Sciences Corporation Pegasus XL launch vehicle. Total spacecraft mass will be less than 275 kg. Orbit average power consumed will be less than 175 W.

The WIRE instrument will be delivered to NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center in early 1998 to undergo integration and test with the WIRE spacecraft bus and subsequently will be launched in the fall of 1998. The SMEX program uses a strict design-to-cost approach to manage and to contain overall mission cost. This paper will present the major instrument, operational and cost requirements driving the

spacecraft systems design for the mechanical, structural, thermal, attitude control, command and data handling, power and electrical systems. It will document major system trade studies results and the subsequent spacecraft design to meet mission requirements.

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1. INTRODUCTION

The Small Explorer Project at NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center (GSFC) is a cost-constrained, rapid-development, partnership with the scientific community to develop and

to fly astrophysics and space science missions. Instrument contract awards are competitive and selection is based upon scientific merit as determined by review committees selected by NASA Headquarters. The selected instruments are custom designed by each principal investigator/developer team.

The SMEX Project office at NASA/GSFC provides the spacecraft bus and contracts for launch vehicle and support services. Development costs are minimized for the spacecraft by reusing hardware and software subsystem designs from previous missions whenever and wherever possible. Some customization of the actual spacecraft bus package is permitted to satisfy instrument interface requirements or other mission unique requirements. Standard attitude control, data handling, computer, electrical, power and communications systems and interfaces are used whenever possible. Most components are single-string, eliminating the cost and complexity associated with building and testing redundant hardware, while accepting some additional risk. The contractual use of multiple buys for hardware helps keep procurement costs down. Selected high payoff technology infusion items are pursued and this implies the SMEX spacecraft bus does evolve over multiple missions.

The Wide-Field Infrared Explorer (WIRE) is the fifth SMEX mission. The first mission, the Solar Anomalous and Magnetospheric Particle Explorer (SAMPEX) was launched on July 3, 1992 on a Scout rocket. SAMPEX discovered a new radiation belt around the earth. It continues to perform without any failures. The Fast Auroral Snapshot (FAST) was ready to launch in August 1994, and the Submillimeter Wave Astronomy Satellite (SWAS) was ready to launch in July 1995. Both missions are waiting for the Pegasus XL. The fourth SMEX mission is the Transition

Region and Coronal Explorer (TRACE) [1]. TRACE is scheduled for a September 1997 launch.

WIRE (see Figure 1) carries a cryogenically-cooled, infrared telescope designed to conduct a survey of distant starburst galaxies 500 times fainter than the existing baseline which was gathered by the Infra-Red Astronomy Satellite (IRAS) and documented in the IRAS Faint Source Survey Catalog. WIRE will answer the following questions: (1) What fraction of the luminosity of the universe at a redshift of 0.5 and beyond is due to starburst galaxies? (2) How fast and in what ways are starburst galaxies evolving? (3) Are luminous protogalaxies common at redshifts less than 3?

The survey will consist of repeated observations at high galactic latitudes, away from the dust and gas in the galactic plane. The spacecraft will point the telescope at a selected point in the sky, the instrument will integrate the 33 x 33 arcminute image for 64 seconds, then the spacecraft will offset the telescope by about one arcminute, and the instrument will take another 64 second exposure. This process will continue for about 15 minutes, until the earth gets too close to the instrument boresight (see earth avoidance information in the Attitude Control System section). The spacecraft will revisit certain targets on the following orbits to increase the total exposure time. On the ground, the operators will background-subtract, flat-field, register, and co-add images to produce detections of at least 30,000 starburst galaxies, revealing evolutionary history out to a redshift of 0.5-1 and the evolutionary history of extremely luminous galaxies beyond redshifts of 5. The observation strategy is designed to improve the signal-to-noise ratio of the starburst galaxies as much as possible in an environment where the "background" noise from local dust and gas is 1000 times *greater*

Figure 1. WIRE Spacecraft

than the signal. This survey demands high performance from the attitude control system (less than 6 arcsecond jitter, 1 sigma).

The WIRE mission [2] [3] was proposed by the Jet Propulsion Laboratory (JPL) and Utah State University's Space Dynamics Lab (SDL) in January of 1993 as a response to NASA's announcement of opportunity for the second set of Small Explorers. Mission definition work was finished in August of 1994. In the fall of 1994, NASA selected WIRE for full-scale development starting in October 1995. A small amount of funding was available in 1995 for a "bridge phase" where critical issues were worked.

In order to minimize cost, the WIRE concept at the end of the definition phase called for a replication of the SWAS spacecraft, with the

WIRE instrument replacing the SWAS instrument. The attitude control system safehold would require modification to provide earth avoidance, but otherwise the spacecraft structure and electronics would be the same. SWAS is a three-axis stabilized spacecraft with arc-second-class pointing.

NASA/Goddard Space Flight Center will provide the spacecraft bus, integrate the instrument with the spacecraft, and perform integrated spacecraft functional and environmental testing. The WIRE spacecraft will be launched into a 440 km by 520 km sun-synchronous orbit by the Orbital Science Corporation's Pegasus XL. GSFC will operate the spacecraft, the PI will perform target selection, and the Infrared Processing Facility (IPAC) at Caltech/JPL will be

responsible for data reduction, analysis, and archiving.

2. INSTRUMENT

The telescope is a Ritchey-Chretien Cassegrain design with a 30 cm aperture, 3.3 focal ratio, and a 33 x 33 arcminute field of view. The primary and secondary mirrors are diamond turned aluminum. A dichroic beam splitter and an optical band pass filter separate the focused infrared energy for viewing in two color bands (12 and 25 micrometers wavelengths). The infrared images are then captured by two 128 x 128 pixel arsenic-doped silicon detector arrays fabricated by Rockwell International.

To keep the design simple and to control costs, there are no moving parts in the WIRE instrument. The entire optical assembly is an integral, independent module which plugs into the cryostat. The cryostat is a two stage, solid hydrogen design fabricated by Lockheed Palo Alto Research Lab. The cryostat will cool the detector arrays to 7.5 Kelvin and the optics to about 12 Kelvin for a period of 4 months using 5 kg of hydrogen. Solid hydrogen makes this mission possible on a Small Explorer--we would need about 100 kg of helium (and a much larger tank) for an equivalent lifetime, and no other cryogen can get the detectors to 7.5 Kelvin. The entire instrument mass will be less than 93 kg.

The Utah State University Space Dynamic Lab will design and fabricate the telescope optical components and integrate them with the cryostat.

Once the spacecraft is placed into orbit, the hydrogen tank primary and secondary vents will be opened by pyro initiators within several hours. An instrument aperture cover will remain in place for up to five days. This

permits offgassing of volatile materials from the spacecraft and dispersion into space prior to aperture cover ejection. By doing so, we hope to minimize freeze-out of these volatile materials on the telescope and detector cryogenic surfaces. Contamination of this sort could drastically reduce the sensitivity of the instrument and jeopardize the WIRE mission from achieving its scientific objectives.

3. ORBIT

WIRE's sun-synchronous full-sun orbit reduces the battery and solar array size and simplifies the instrument design. The required lifetime for the spacecraft is 120 days: 20 days for setup, calibration, and initial checkout and 3 million seconds of exposure time at 35% observing efficiency. The orbit was chosen to maximize mass-to-orbit given the worst-case performance of the Pegasus vehicle and moderately high solar flux. For a 470 x 540 km nominal orbit, the worst-case Pegasus insertion (without failures) is a 450 km circular orbit. Assuming a 2×10^6 Jansky (Jy) solar flux at 10.7 cm wavelength ($1 \text{ Jy} = 10^{-26} \text{ W/m}^2\text{-Hz}$) and a 0.015 m^2/kg ballistic coefficient, the orbit lifetime from 450 km is 4 months (to 400 km where the ACS begins to have control problems). The flux level, which drives the atmospheric density, is high for a 1998 launch, but we did not want the spacecraft to be too heavy to launch near solar maximum in 1999 or 2000. The Pegasus XL can put 275 kg into a 470 x 540 km sun-synchronous orbit. Taking into account dispersions and the four month full-sun requirement, WIRE's launch window is four months long twice per year--a spring launch into a 6am ascending-node orbit and a fall launch into a 6pm orbit. Science observing constraints may shorten the launch window by a week or two on each end. Three months twice per year is a reasonable launch window for a Small Explorer.

4. SPACECRAFT STRUCTURE

Using the measured mass from SWAS and the estimated mass of the WIRE instrument, the total spacecraft mass *without margin* was 270 kg when we selected the 470 x 540 km orbit. WIRE had already been slated for technology development funds for a composite structure, and preliminary investigations showed that development of this structure was relatively low-risk, so we have baselined a newly-designed composite structure. The current spacecraft mass estimate is 250 kg, and we are actively pursuing further mass reduction throughout the spacecraft (see section 12. System Design Issues).

As mentioned earlier, composites are potential contamination sources for the instrument. Structural as well as thermal composites will be used on WIRE. Samples must be tested to determine total volatility, before and after vacuum conditioning and subsequent water absorption prior to launch. Outgassing rates must be determined and factored into a molecular transport model. Results from this effort will affect the aperture cover ejection timeline. Additional testing must be done to insure that the thermal conductivity is not degraded by vibration during I&T and launch.

The WIRE spacecraft is octagonal with an upper, middle, and lower deck. Most electronics boxes mount to the inside of radiator panels around the perimeter of the spacecraft, providing good thermal control (see section 5. Thermal Control). A set of four bi-podal struts, arranged in a triangular fashion, was selected as the mechanical interface between instrument and spacecraft bus. These struts connect to the spacecraft bus upper deck and were to connect to the instrument at a reinforced aluminum girth ring fastened to the cryostat pressure wall. Fabrication and concerns about alignment and

integration of the instrument to the spacecraft forced a redesign of this girth ring concept. Instead, four mounting pads will be machined into the instrument dewar pressure wall. The strut assemblies will be attached to the spacecraft bus as before, but now alignment/load bearing pins will be drilled during final assembly and non-critical tolerance bolts will complete the assembly process.

GSFC is investigating the use of gamma alumina as a potential strut material. This material has a very low thermal conductivity with acceptable strength and toughness properties. Cryogen life is very much dependent on the environmental heat load into the instrument. This environmental heat load comes from earth albedo, spacecraft bus radiation and heat conduction down the instrument support struts. The initial baseline for the strut material was M55J composite. Going to gamma alumina would extend the cryostat life by as much as two weeks. This is significant when you consider the expected maximum mission life is only four months. Because GSFC has no previous experience with gamma alumina, test pieces have been ordered to qualify its use for WIRE. Titanium (6AL-4V) has been identified as a reasonable second choice. Its thermal conductivity is only slightly higher than gamma alumina.

5. THERMAL CONTROL

The spacecraft uses radiators, blankets, and heaters to control temperatures within -10° to $+40^{\circ}$ C for most electronics. The primary electronic boxes each mount to an efficient radiator panel made of K1100/954-3, quasi-isotropic composite with a thermal conductivity of 350 W/m-K. The radiating area for each box is sized based on the box's power dissipation, and a blanket covers the excess radiating area. Thermostatically

controlled heaters keep boxes above their survival temperatures when they are off.

The battery has a particularly narrow operating range (0° to 20° C). It has a highly efficient radiator on the anti-sun side of the structure. Operational heaters keep it in the correct temperature range. The battery must be on the outside of the spacecraft so that it can be kept cool (below 20° C) during ground testing just prior to launch.

The thermal design is based on a detailed model which is verified during a thermal balance test of the spacecraft in a vacuum chamber.

6. POWER SYSTEM

The spacecraft uses a direct energy transfer system where the gallium arsenide solar arrays are diode-ored directly onto the main power buss. The battery is also directly across the buss, providing the voltage reference for the system. All electronics operating off the main spacecraft power must handle 28 ± 7 V. We also require survival of 0 to 40 V indefinitely without damage to protect against mistakes during ground tests.

The battery charge control circuitry shorts half strings of the solar array as the battery reaches a pre-set voltage, tapering the battery current. This voltage varies automatically with temperature. When the amp-hour integrator (AHI) circuit determines that the battery is fully charged, a current controller takes over and maintains a constant 90 mA battery trickle charge. Both the voltage/temperature (V/T) controller and the AHI are analog circuits, providing battery charge control independent of the spacecraft computer.

Because of its full-sun orbit, WIRE is not constrained to a battery which can survive

thousands of charge/discharge cycles, such as a nickel-cadmium (Ni-Cd) battery. Several options are currently under consideration (see section 12. System Design Issues).

7. ATTITUDE CONTROL SYSTEM

The SWAS attitude control system (ACS) is a three-axis stabilized, zero-momentum system. It has four reaction wheels for control and three magnetic torque rods for momentum dumping. For attitude determination, a Ball CT-601 star tracker and a gyro pack provide the primary inputs to a Kalman filter algorithm running on the spacecraft's 386 processor. For safehold, the y-axis wheel (along the sun line) runs at a fixed rate, and an analog circuit implements a B-dot controller (current in the magnetic torquers is proportional to the rate of change of the magnetic field) for rate damping and a bang-bang sun precession controller. Safehold uses the three magnetic torque rods for control and a three-axis magnetometer, digital sun sensor, and six coarse sun sensors for determination. Although SMEX missions are generally single-string, the extra wheel and an extra gyro provide some redundancy for certain failures.

The primary challenge in adapting the SWAS attitude control system to WIRE relates to WIRE's earth and sun avoidance constraints. In order to prevent excessive cryogen loss, the limb of the earth and the limb of the sun must remain more than 80° from the boresight of the telescope. Also, if the sun gets within several degrees of the boresight of the instrument, it will instantly destroy parts of the optics.

WIRE's primary targets are located away from the ecliptic and near the galactic poles, parts of the sky with minimal foreground dust. Because of the sun-synchronous orbit, the sun

is always within 20° of orbit normal. Because of the earth avoidance constraint, the telescope must always look within 30° of zenith. Therefore, the observation sequences will each be about 1/6 of the orbit (60°). The spacecraft will point the instrument at a preselected target when the target is within 30° of zenith. The spacecraft attitude will remain approximately constant on the target (there is a one arcminute dither between one minute exposures) until the earth limb is just over 80° from the boresight. The spacecraft will then slew 60+° to the next target and begin the next observation.

Changes from the SWAS baseline were necessary to meet the new earth avoidance constraint and the tighter sun avoidance constraint of WIRE. A coarse earth sensor was added to provide a reference for earth avoidance control and constraint checking. Several pointing modes were modified to account for this new constraint. Since the large slew maneuvers will be predominately about the y-axis (x- and z-axis rotations will be small), the spacecraft will maintain a momentum bias toward the sun throughout the entire mission. WIRE's momentum bias aides in meeting the sun constraint by providing passive stability about the sunline.

The attitude control system will have six different pointing modes: analog safehold, attitude control electronics (ACE) safehold, spacecraft computer system (SCS) safehold, zenith sunpoint, transitional stellar acquisition, and stellar point (normal mode). These modes are listed in hierarchical order, with analog safehold being the lowest level. Downward transitions from normal mode are autonomous, protecting the spacecraft from anomalous conditions. Upward transitions are initiated by ground command, allowing the spacecraft operators to verify the safety of the

spacecraft before and after the transition. The different modes allow graceful transitions and a quick return to normal operations [4].

Analog safehold is active only when the 8085 processor in the ACE box has "hung up" for some reason. This is the same safehold which is flying on SAMPEX and SWAS. It provides the same functions as ACE safehold except for earth avoidance.

ACE safehold is the default power-up state of the spacecraft. ACE safehold damps body rates, points the solar arrays at the sun, and points the instrument boresight away from the earth. These functions are accomplished with a minimal set of hardware and software running on the ACE box 8085 processor. ACE safehold is the safety net which protects the spacecraft from serious anomalies such as software upsets in the main processor. ACE safehold is the mode used for initial acquisition after launch.

SCS safehold is ACE safehold implemented with the spacecraft processor. It provides a graceful transition from ACE box control to the processor's software control.

Zenith sunpoint uses the sun vector and the magnetic field vector measurements along with a magnetic field model and a solar model to determine the attitude of the spacecraft. It then uses the momentum wheels to point the solar array toward the sun and the instrument boresight toward zenith. This mode requires the ground to uplink an orbit ephemeris for WIRE.

Transitional stellar acquisition points the instrument toward one of TBD (2) pre-defined points so that the star tracker can acquire stars. The attitude control system uses the normal mode algorithms for attitude determination and control.

Normal mode is the science targeting mode in which the spacecraft collects science data. While pointing at a target, the spacecraft takes multiple one-minute exposures, with a slight offset (60 arcseconds) between each. The jitter requirement while on target is 6 arcseconds (1σ).

8. COMMAND AND DATA HANDLING

For communications, WIRE uses an S-band transponder. When an uplink is present, the downlink frequency is coherent with the uplink, providing the capability of two-way Doppler tracking for orbit determination. The transponder also has range tone capability, but the Doppler tracking provides sufficient orbit accuracy. Orbit determination accuracy is

driven by knowing when targets will be visible and by the accuracy required for attitude determination using the magnetic field model.

The transponder interfaces directly to the spacecraft computer system (SCS). The SCS's 80386 microprocessor with 387 coprocessor host the command and data handling (C&DH) software as well as the ACS software. The SCS contains a 300 Mbyte memory card, miscellaneous I/O ports (such as RS-232), the spacecraft clock, and a hardware command timer used for solar array deployment after launch. The spacecraft controls all data flow using a MIL-STD-1553 data buss (see Figure 2).

Figure 2. WIRE Data Flow Diagram

Sophisticated software makes this high-performance, cost-constrained spacecraft possible. Written in C, the object-oriented code is very portable and reusable. An ACS mathematics library which was created for SWAS can be reused with no changes for both TRACE and WIRE. Excellent developers working with good debugging and test tools make the code fairly reliable. Hardware watchdog timers cover for the inevitable bug or upset, rebooting the computer.

9. GROUND SYSTEM

The operational ground systems at Goddard have historically been different from the systems used during the integration and test (I&T) of the spacecraft. SMEX is currently working toward a common system based on the I&T system we have used for SAMPEX, FAST, and SWAS. It seems obvious that the same system should be used, but the money for operations currently comes from a different pot than the spacecraft development money. With the recent cuts in NASA's budget, the ground operation organization is much more willing to work toward a common system which is not overly complex or expensive to implement.

By using the same system for I&T and operations, we will get as much time on our ground system as we get on the spacecraft (over 1000 hours). More time on the system equates to more reliability (since more of the software bugs are discovered). The operators also get more time running the spacecraft as it will function on orbit.

The ground system software runs on a UNIX-based workstation (or PC). Additional hardware provides bit and frame synchronization, recording of the raw telemetry stream, and simulation of the launch vehicle interface during I&T. Each subsystem

lead uses a dedicated workstation to display telemetry during critical tests such as thermal vacuum and during early orbit operations.

10. HYDROGEN FILL

With a payload containing hydrogen, WIRE has some special safety and operational concerns. The cryostat must be initially precooled by flowing gaseous helium through tubing wrapped around the hydrogen storage tanks. This precooling may take several days. Gaseous hydrogen is then admitted to the primary and secondary hydrogen tanks where it cools, liquefies, solidifies and is subsequently subcooled as much as 10 degrees. This process is expected to occur in one to two days. Once the tanks are filled, hydrogen supply lines will be disconnected and fill ports will be capped. Gaseous helium must be flowed for at least one day every week prior to launch to keep the hydrogen solidified. These operational limitations drive the launch site processing flow path. The hydrogen fill will occur in a special building at the launch site. This building has a clean tent with explosion proof electronics and emergency exhaust vents in the roof. After the fill is complete, the risk of a hydrogen leak is substantially lower. In the event of a hydrogen or vacuum leak, the primary hydrogen vent path is the emergency vent line which connects five burst disks into a common manifold. The vent line is connected to a vent stack which has a nitrogen purge. (The nitrogen prevents a flammable mixture of hydrogen and oxygen in the vent line.). A special fly-away venting system is required while the Pegasus is attached to the L-1011 prior to drop.

11. TESTING

The SMEX development philosophy stresses a thorough test program. It is pointless to waste months of effort on the analysis of some part

which can be fabricated in a week and tested the next week. No one would feel comfortable with the analysis until a test was run anyway. We perform interface tests and fit checks as soon as breadboards and engineering mock-ups are available. There is a problem every time two systems are brought together. These problems are unforeseen and probably unforeseeable, so it makes sense to find them with a test as early as possible. The extreme complexity and non-linearity [5] of software demands a substantial amount of test time after the last software modification. Tests must approximate flight conditions as much as possible to help flush out those unforeseeable problems.

The SMEX spacecraft typically spend almost a year of the three year development cycle in the integration and test (I&T) phase. Automated test procedures send commands to and monitor telemetry from the spacecraft. For the safety of the spacecraft, all testing is controlled by a test conductor. The test conductor starts the procedures, monitors their progress, and sends real-time commands at the direction of the subsystem lead in charge of the test. Each subsystem lead writes the tests for his subsystem, and the system engineer reviews them. The system engineer writes the spacecraft system level tests, and the subsystem leads review them. The automated procedures are run throughout environmental testing, looking for degradation, software bugs, and design problems which might jeopardize the mission.

Environmental testing includes electro-magnetic interference and compatibility, vibration, acoustics, thermal balance (testing the thermal system), thermal vacuum, and magnetic calibration (for the ACS magnetometer). The day-long spacecraft functional test, exercising all nominal mission functions, is run between each environmental

test, after each spacecraft move, and at each plateau of the four cycle thermal vacuum test. The two-week-long comprehensive test, verifying all spacecraft functions, is run before and after environmental testing. A daily trending test measures key parameters, such as currents and noise levels, which are plotted weekly for trend analysis. During a week-long end-to-end test, the flight operations team (FOT) runs the spacecraft as if it were on orbit, with an ACS dynamic simulator mimicking attitude sensor data, while the engineering team introduces anomalies which the FOT must handle. By the time we launch a Small Explorer, it has over 1000 hours of test time, and we are fairly confident it will perform its mission. WIRE will run through the same program, with the added complexity of cryogenic operations.

12. SYSTEM DESIGN ISSUES

The low mass margin has been the primary concern throughout the bridge phase. There was some indication of low mass margin at the end of the definition phase. A composite structure was selected as a technology development area, and a relatively low orbit (400 km) was baselined for the four month mission.

The real crunch in mass came during the bridge phase, and it came from both ends. A more detailed look at orbit requirements showed that the large Pegasus XL launch dispersions (+/- 90 km on apogee) could put WIRE too low for a 400 km circular orbit. Also, because of the approaching solar maximum, atmospheric drag could potentially limit even a 420 km orbit to less than four months. The drag also affects the performance of the attitude control system below 400 km. The other side of the crunch came as the cryostat design started, and the engineers discovered that the cryostat mass

estimate should be 50% higher. The instrument used up more than all of its mass margin, and the baseline orbit was too low. The combined mass hit on the 250 kg spacecraft amounted to almost 40 kg. Even though the spacecraft bus masses are very mature (we have measured values from SWAS), the instrument design has a long way to go. We were forced into a redesign of the structure, with the composite technology becoming very important. Meanwhile, mass became a driving factor in all instrument and spacecraft design decisions. The current mass distribution is shown in Table 1.

Table 1. WIRE Mass Distribution

SUBSYSTEM	MASS (kg)
Instrument	85
Structure	50
Thermal	6
Power	35
ACS	44
SCS	11
RF System	5
Harness	14
TOTAL	250

Because of the cost-constraints on SMEX missions, WIRE's mass growth could have quickly led to termination without cost savings elsewhere. WIRE has taken advantage of the mature design of SWAS components and the electronics build for TRACE by fabricating the attitude control electronics (ACE), the spacecraft computer system (SCS), and the spacecraft power electronics (SPE) boxes simultaneously with TRACE. The substantial cost savings is well worth the decrease in flexibility of the design, but it does occasionally reduce the possible options.

With battery charge control circuits already being built and a 9 A-hr Ni-Cd flight spare on the shelf, there is strong motivation to stay with a Ni-Cd battery. To complicate matters, the group at GSFC in charge of battery procurement is reluctant to fly batteries that do not have a long history of flight on NASA satellites, again driving us toward flight-proven Ni-Cd batteries. Unfortunately, the mass problem and the short mission life push the design toward a higher energy density technology such as silver zinc (Ag-Z). The battery is also driving the height of the spacecraft, so any increase in size of the battery will increase the height of the spacecraft, increasing the structure's mass and disrupting interfaces between the instrument and the launch vehicle fairing (door placement and hydrogen venting).

The 9 A-hr in-stock battery was the baseline at the end of the definition phase, but this battery capacity is marginal for the initial sun acquisition following separation from the launch vehicle. The B-dot safhold controller used for initial acquisition is extremely robust, but it requires up to 150 minutes for B-dot to damp the potentially high Pegasus tip-off rates (up to 5.6 degrees/sec) and the safhold precession controller to point the solar arrays at the sun. Up to 8 A-hr of capacity can be consumed during this time. The time can be reduced, but at the expense of stability (and sun avoidance for the instrument) once the spacecraft captures the sun. A more complicated algorithm could be used, but at the expense of the reliability of safhold, our spacecraft's safety net. Right now we are pursuing three battery options: a Ag-Z battery with 12 or more A-hr of capacity, a Ni-Cd secondary (rechargeable) battery augmented with a high energy density primary battery, or a common pressure vessel nickel-hydrogen (Ni-H) battery. The Ag-Z option looks best since mass is so critical. The Ni-Cd secondary

battery with augmentation has no impact on our existing battery charging circuitry. The primary battery would connect to the buss through a diode, so it would not be recharged. This battery could be a sounding rocket battery, since it only operates for the first several hours after launch. The Ni-H option is recommended by our battery engineers as the conservative approach. Although a 15 A-hr Ni-H battery is about the same mass as the in-stock 9 A-hr Ni-Cd, its dimensions are awkward in the WIRE structure, causing additional mass uncertainty.

The attitude control system (ACS) is the most expensive and complicated aspect of the spacecraft bus. It is also the part of the system (other than the structure) which is most driven by unique instrument requirements. The sun avoidance and earth avoidance constraints (see section 7. Attitude Control System) have driven the bridge phase ACS design trades.

Because any shutter mechanism on the instrument would have to operate at cryogenic temperatures, we put the burden on the ACS to avoid the sun through all survivable failure scenarios (failures after which the spacecraft could still carry out its mission, such as a bad uplinked command). This requirement coupled with relatively small ($\pm 10^\circ$) slews out of the plane perpendicular to the sun-line enabled us to add a momentum bias along the sun-line during normal operations. The bias stiffens the system along the sun-line, perpendicular to the instrument axis, allowing the spacecraft more time to react to anomalies. This bias will be of the same magnitude as the bias used by safehold to minimize body rates during a transition to safehold.

The earth avoidance requirement has driven a change to the SWAS safehold. The original safehold controller had only B-dot rate

damping around the sun-line; the spacecraft would rotate at a twice-per-orbit rate, slewing the instrument through the earth. We have incorporated a differential pair of earth sensors which look out the +x and -x axis. The ACE box 8085 controller software will read the data from the earth sensors and control the y-wheel speed to keep the instrument pointed zenith. The SWAS safehold was entirely analog for maximum reliability, but we have chosen a software solution which uses the analog signals and a simple algorithm in order to minimize hardware changes and maximize commonality with TRACE.

The use of solid hydrogen, and the resulting safety concerns of launching WIRE from a manned L-1011, have introduced significant complications in the development of an emergency vent system that will work during launch site processing, hot pad operations, captive carry and launch abort scenarios. It has been a big driver in finalizing the spacecraft and launch vehicle processing flow path at Vandenburg. A successful resolution of safety issues can only be accomplished by achieving a consensus among the multiple government and contractor organizations.

A final system design issue worth including here is packaging. Locating the star tracker, instrument plumbing, emergency hydrogen vent, earth sensors, torque rods, antennas, transponders and instrument aperture shade has not been an easy task. There have been many iterations on the mechanical, electrical and structural interfaces to minimize mutual interference and stay within the dynamic envelop of the Pegasus XL launch vehicle.

13. FUTURE WORK

The top priority for WIRE right now is detailing interfaces and communicating requirements via the system requirements

document. The latest version of WIRE's system requirements document is accessible to everyone working on WIRE via Internet [6]. This hypertext format allows a common location for requirements which apply to multiple subsystems--each link referencing a given requirement points to the same document. Pending changes can be posted prior to official approval, so the full impact of the change can be assessed.

14. CONCLUSIONS

When the Wide-Field Infrared Explorer is launched in the fall of 1998, it will provide unprecedented views of the infrared sky. This cost-constrained mission is possible because of the miniaturization of electronics and the maturity and complexity of software systems.

All the components of a small spacecraft must fit together in a package which is usually too small and too heavy. Items as diverse as battery chemistry, launch vehicle tip-off, and sun shades are traded against each other in terms of their impact on mass, power, and cost.

There are certain items which we know we don't know and we label as TBD, such as the maximum offset acceptable between the star tracker and the instrument boresights. We perform tests and analyses to eliminate these unknowns as quickly as possible. Then there are the items which we do not even know we should worry about. These are the problems which destroy missions. These are the problems which our test program tries to flush out. It is the continuing challenge of the system engineer to seek out the unknown unknowns and maintain a system which is robust enough to handle the ones which are missed.

15. ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

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16. REFERENCES

- [1] J. Burt, "Transition Region and Coronal Explorer Mission," elsewhere in this proceeding.
- [2] H. Schember and P. Hacking, "The Wide-Field Infrared Explorer," *Infrared Spaceborne Remote Sensing*, SPIE Proceedings 2019, p395-406 (1993).
- [3] D. Elliot, P. Hacking and H. Schember, "Engineering Design of the Wide-Field Infrared Explorer (WIRE)," SPIE Annual Meeting, San Diego, CA, July 1994.
- [4] D. Everett and T. Trenkle, "Robust Safing for Small, Low-Cost Satellites," Supplemental Proceedings of the 9th Annual AIAA/USU Conference on Small Satellites, September 18-21, 1995.
- [5] B. Littlewood and L. Strigini, "The Risks of Software," *Scientific American*, November 1992, p. 62-75.
- [6] <http://sunland.gsfc.nasa.gov/smex/wire/sysreq/concept.html>

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